

STUDIES IN GLASS SYSTEMS. REFRACTOMETRIC STUDIES OF ALKALI HALIDES DISSOLVED IN BORAX GLASS

BY SUBODH KUMAR MAJUMDAR AND BHUPATI KUMAR BANERJEE

Salts like LiCl, NaCl, KCl and NaI were dissolved in fused borax glass and the mole-refraction of the solidified glasses were determined. The mole-refraction of the dissolved salts calculated from the additivity formula shows considerable departure from values in the crystalline state and at infinite dilution. The concentration—mole. refraction curves for all these salts show a positive slope unlike the case in aqueous solutions. But the values are considerably smaller than those of the crystal and for infinite dilution, showing the existence of a very considerable deformation in the glass system. The positive character of the slope is explained as due to decreased dissociation of the salt in the glass medium. On the whole Fajans deformation rule is qualitatively established for solid solutions of these salts in glass systems.

Fajans and co-workers have done a considerable amount of work on the mole-refraction of different salts, possessing ions of inert gas configuration, in the solid crystalline state, in the state of vapour and in aqueous solutions (Fajans and Joos, *Z. Physik*, 1924, 23, 1; Fajans, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 357; Fajans, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1928, 34, 502; Wulff and Schaller, *Z. Krist.*, 1934, 87, 43; Geffcken, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, B 5, 81, etc.). Majumdar and co-workers (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, B, 31, 319; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 241, 461; 1946, 23, 317; 1945, 22, 147) have studied the behaviour of different polar salts dissolved in boric oxide and borax glasses. With the alkali halides, dissolved in boric oxide glass, they have found that these salts are very strongly deformed in solid solution and the relative deforming power of the cations on the common anion obeys Fajans deformation rule qualitatively. It was therefore thought interesting to extend the studies to as many glass solvent media as possible. An added advantage which such systems possess over those studied before is that the samples are less liable to the action of moisture and they therefore remain clear quite a long time.

The deforming action of the ions of a molecule on each other and on the surrounding solvent medium may be classified as follows :—

(i)	Action of the cation on the anion	.. Decrease in mole-refraction
(ii)	" anion " cation	.. Increase "
(iii)	" anion on the solvent	.. Increase "
(iv)	" cation "	.. Decrease "

A typical example of the decrease of mole-refraction with concentration is furnished by LiCl in aqueous solution. A decrease in the mole-refraction value occurs by the transition of LiCl at infinite dilution to the state of the crystal. Thus

$$\Delta R = R_{\text{cryst.}} - R_{\text{sol.}} = 7.59 - 8.74 = -1.45.$$

In this case owing to the small ionic diameter of Li⁺ ion and its strong hydration, the effects (i) and (iv) preponderate over those of (ii) and (iii) and hence the mole-refraction—concentration curve shows a negative slope. In the case of crystal, the effect of

deformation is maximum and hence minimum value of mole-refraction is given by it. And this is true in a greater or lesser degree with aqueous solutions, according to concentration. In the case of a salt like KF, on the other hand, the effect of the anion on the cation is greater than that of cation on anion and thus the mole-refraction—concentration curve shows a positive slope. As has been shown by Majumdar *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) with boric oxide as the solvent medium and as will appear from the present paper, a much smaller value of mole-refraction is obtained for LiCl when dissolved in such glasses.

According to the Lorenz-Lorentz formula, the mole-refraction R of a pure substance is given by

$$R = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{d} \quad (1)$$

where n is the refractive index and d , the density of the substance and M , its molecular weight. Strictly speaking n should be the refractive index for infinitely long wave-length, if R is to be taken as a measure of the polarisability of the molecule. In this case $n^2 = \epsilon$, where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the medium and the Lorenz-Lorentz equation changes to the well known Clausius-Mosotti equation. For the purpose of comparison, however, the refractive index for a particular visible wave-length (D-line) may be taken without serious error. In a glass system consisting of p per cent of alkali chloride XCl and therefore of $(100 - p)$ per cent borax, if r be the specific refraction of the glass mixture, r_1 , that of the alkali chloride and r_2 , the value for fused borax glass, then the following relation should hold good, if the additivity rule is obeyed by the mixture :

$$100 r = p.r_1 + (100 - p).r_2 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The specific refraction r of the glass mixture can be calculated from the experimental values of n and d from the formula

$$r = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{1}{d}$$

The value of r_2 can be similarly found from pure fused borax glass. Hence from equation (2), the specific refraction of the dissolved alkali halide and hence its mole-refraction may be calculated. This is on the assumption, however, that the refractivity of the solvent remains unchanged. This value of mole-refraction of XCl in glass may be conveniently compared with its values in the crystal and in aqueous solution at infinite dilution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the samples.—An aqueous solution of LiCl, which as is well known is hygroscopic, was evaporated to dryness in a platinum crucible and the residue quickly taken up with absolute alcohol. There was usually a small insoluble residue left. The alcoholic solution was filtered and the alcohol evaporated off. The residue was kept in a vacuum desiccator before use. The other chemicals (Merck, pro-Analyse quality) were recrystallised once and used. Borax was powdered and dehydrated first in a hot air oven and then in a vacuum desiccator for several days, until a sample taken up with absolute alcohol did not impart any coloration to anhydrous CuSO_4 . Complete dehydration of borax before fusion is necessary, as otherwise the glasses tenaciously retain traces of moisture which would be difficult to remove later (*cf.* Consen and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 2654). The salts were similarly dehydrated beforehand and different samples of

borax and alkali halides were powdered and heated in a platinum crucible in an electric furnace to about 1000° until a thoroughly homogeneous melt was obtained. The platinum crucible was then chilled and the solidified glass extracted. A portion of the ingredients first sublimed but later a melt of constant composition was obtained. Each sample was examined in a Polarisation microscope and only those pieces which were optically isotropic were taken. Platinum possesses a different coefficient of expansion from the melt and hence when the melt solidifies great stress is brought to bear on the system with the result that there is chance of the solid being double refracting. It should be noticed that although borax crystals are optically anisotropic, borax glass, if properly prepared, is isotropic. This is an additional proof of Warren's view that in a glass the constituents form a sort of non-periodic network as opposed to the periodic space lattice present in a true crystal.

Analysis of the samples.—The halogen content of the samples was determined at first volumetrically by back titration method and then checked in some cases by gravimetric precipitation. About 1.5 g. of the glass was dissolved in hot water and made up to 100 c.c. An aliquot part was taken and treated with a definite volume of standard AgNO_3 adding excess of nitric acid. The excess of silver nitrate was back titrated against standard NH_4CNS using ferric alum as indicator.

Density determination.—The densities of the samples were determined according to the method detailed in a previous paper (Majumdar and Sarma, *loc. cit.*). A small particle of the glass was suspended in a mixture of acetylene tetrabromide and toluene and the container vessel kept in a transparent thermostat maintained at 35° . The composition of the suspension liquid was altered until the particle remained suspended in any position. The exact point was reached by noting the movement of the particle several times up and down. At this point the liquid mixture was introduced into a weighed pycnometer joined by a tube with ground glass stopper and also placed in the thermostat. The usual precautions were taken and the weight of the pycnometer again determined. Two independent determinations were made with each sample and the mean value taken.

Refractive Index determination.—The refractive index of the samples was determined by the Becke method followed by the determination of the refractive indices of the two liquid mixtures in a Pulfrich refractometer, sodium light from an Osram sodium lamp being used for both the measurements. It is well known that refractive index determination of solids presents considerable difficulties. Direct determination of refractive index of a solid is possible in a Pulfrich refractometer if the solid is ground in the shape of a right angled prism with optical plane faces. This is, however, not possible in the present case.

A small piece of the solid was suspended in a liquid mixture and focussed in sodium light in a high power microscope. The composition of the liquid was then varied and the eye piece was raised after focussing. If the refractive indices of the solid and liquid are very nearly equal, either of the two effects are observed on raising the eye piece; either the outline of the solid-liquid recede away from the solid or the lines seem to enter the solid. In the former case the refractive index of the solid is less than that of the liquid and *vice versa*. Hence by choosing two liquids, one having a higher and the other a lower refractive index than the solid and adjusting the composition carefully, two liquid

mixtures may be obtained, the refractive indices of which are respectively only slightly higher and slightly lower than the solid itself. The refractive indices of these two are then accurately determined in a Pulfrich refractometer and the mean value taken; the two values usually varied in the fourth place of decimal. The determinations had to be carried out at room temperature, but as solids possess a very small temperature coefficient of refractive index (less than the experimental error in this case), this introduced no serious error in the comparative values.

TABLE I

Cg/100g-Conc. in g. equiv./1000g. borax.				$n_D =$ Ref. index in D-light.			
LiCl-borax glass.				NaCl-borax glass.			
LiCl	Cg/1000 g.	Density.	n_D .	NaCl	Cg/1000 g.	Density.	n_D .
0	0	2.3557	1.5151	5.1%	0.87	2.3349	1.5050
2.0%	0.47	2.3501	1.5089	6.5	1.11	2.3281	1.5031
5.2	1.22	2.3297	1.5038	10.0	1.71	2.3075	1.4958
7.5	1.77	2.3122	1.5022	11.5	1.97	2.2998	1.4950
9.6	2.26	2.2961	1.5011	14.3	2.44	2.2907	1.4944
				14.8	2.53	2.2887	1.4935
				18.8	3.21	2.2653	1.4911
KCl-borax glass.				NaI-borax glass.			
KCl.	Cg/1000 g.	Density.	n_D .	NaI	Cg/1000 g.	Density.	n_D .
7.76%	1.04	2.3296	1.5057	3.12%	0.21	2.3902	1.5154
10.76	1.44	2.3125	1.5047	4.45	0.29	2.4021	1.5159
14.89	1.99	2.2940	1.4997	9.33	0.62	2.4411	1.5219
16.45	2.20	2.2673	1.4955				

In the following tables, r_{XCl} and hence R_{XCl} for the alkali halide dissolved in borax glass are calculated from the mixture law; the respective values of R at infinite dilution and in pure crystal are shown in the last column. The value of r for pure borax is taken as 0.1278 (Wulff and Majumdar, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE II

LiCl-borax glass.						
LiCl.	mix. (obs.)	r_{LiCl} (calc.)	R_{LiCl} (calc.)	R_{sol} .	R_{cryst} .	
2.0%	0.1270	0.0810	3.44			
5.2	0.1268	0.1057	4.47	8.76	7.59	
7.5	0.1276	0.1230	5.22	Fajans, Kohner and Geffcken,		
9.6	0.1283	0.1312	5.57	(Z. Electrochem., 1925, 34, 2)		

TABLE III

NaCl-borax glass.						
NaCl.	r_{mix} (obs.)	r_{NaCl} (calc.)	R_{NaCl} (calc.)	R_{sol}	R_{cryst} .	
5.1%	0.1262	0.0929	5.43			
6.5	0.1269	0.1121	6.55	9.27	8.52	
10.0	0.1265	0.1135	6.63			
11.5	0.1268	0.1177	6.88			
14.3	0.1270	0.1211	7.08			
14.8	0.1269	0.1211	7.08			
18.8	0.1278	0.1273	7.44			

DISCUSSION

With all the four salts investigated, two things come out prominently. First, in every case, the mole-refraction of the dissolved salt increases with concentration and secondly the highest value obtained for the maximum concentration is very considerably smaller than that of the pure salt either in the crystalline condition or in aqueous solution at infinite dilution. The positive slope of the mole-refraction—concentration curve (*vide*

TABLE IV

KCl—borax glass.			
	$R_{\text{sol.}} = 11.31$	$R_{\text{cryst.}} = 10.83$	
KCl	r_{mix} (obs.).	r_{KCl} (calc.).	R_{KCl} (calc.).
7.76%	0.1274	0.1211	9.02
10.76	0.1281	0.1310	9.76
14.89	0.1281	0.1279	9.52
16.45	0.1286	0.1317	9.81

TABLE V

NaI—borax glass.			
	$R_{\text{sol.}} = 19.38$	$R_{\text{cryst.}} = 17.07$	
NaI	r_{mix} (obs.).	r_{NaI} (calc.).	R_{NaI} (calc.).
3.12%	0.1262	0.0702	10.53
4.45	0.1257	0.0737	11.50
9.33	0.1249	0.0948	14.20

FIG. 1

Fig. 1) stands in remarkable contrast to the usual negative slope in aqueous solutions (Fajans, *Z. Elektrochem., loc. cit.*). With the three chlorides investigated, in aqueous solutions, the effects of the cation on the anion and the cation on the solvent medium greatly outweigh the other two effects and hence the mole-refraction decreases with increasing concentration. And it should be remembered in this connection that Li^+ ion most of all and the other two cations in varying degrees are heavily hydrated in solution. The negative slope is very pronounced in the case of NaI in aqueous solution, because the effect (i) has a greater magnitude on the larger iodine ion than in NaCl with a smaller anion. On the other hand, the positive slope of chlorates and sulphates in aqueous solution is explained by the fact that ClO_4^- ion is less polarisable than the water molecule and therefore the effect of the anion on the solvent preponderates. This has been found to be the case with NaClO_4 , LiClO_4 , $\text{Al}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$, the different sulphates and also with KF . Viewed in this light, the positive slope of the curves in the cases investigated in the present paper points either to the interaction of the anion with the solvent medium, not necessarily in a chemical sense, or to a decreased dissociation of the salt with increasing concentration.

It may be mentioned that some exceptions have been found by the workers of the Fajans schools of the general rule that whenever the cation is either small or highly charged and the anion large, the effect of increasing concentration will be increased refraction. Simple nitrates like NaNO_3 , KNO_3 , etc. are found to give a negative slope in aqueous solutions and this is explained by the unsymmetrical distribution of the oxygen octets round the central nitrogen atom in the nitrate ion (Fajans, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1938, 137, 331). In SO_4^{2-} ion on the other hand, the four oxygen octets are symmetrically distributed round the central sulphur atom. And this is also true of ClO_4^- ion.

The positive slope of the curves in aqueous solutions of the above mentioned salts may thus be explained as due to either of the two following effects:—The field of the

cation is so strongly polarised by that of the anion that the polarising effect of the cation on the solvent medium, which brings about decreased refraction, is practically removed and hence a resultant increase of refraction with concentration results. An alternative suggestion is that the hydration layer of the cation is replaced partially (in the case of a polyvalent cation) or wholly by an anion which really amounts to a decreased dissociation of the salt. In the case of salts with polyvalent cations like $\text{Al}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$, therefore ions like $\text{ClO}_4\text{Al}^{++}$ will exist in solution. Hence the effect will be less marked than in the case of a salt like NaClO_4 , in which decreased dissociation of the salt with increased concentration is supposed to be the principal cause of the positive slope. Judged by this standard one can conclude that in the cases of the halides, dissolved in borax glass studied by us, there is evidence of the existence of undissociated molecules. This is understandable from the difference in dielectric constant between water and borate and boric oxide glasses. A negative slope of the curves therefore is not to be expected as in the case of the corresponding aqueous solutions. This does not mean, however, that the dissolved salts retain their lattice dimensions unaltered when in a state of solution in the glass. For reasons explained in previous communications (Majumdar and Palit, *loc. cit.*), an enlargement of lattice dimensions may be expected on theoretical considerations. The experimental evidence on this point, however, has been conflicting (Majumdar, Banerjee and Banerjee, *Nature*, 6th Oct., 1945) and the investigation is being pursued further.

Turning to the experimental results we find that the calculated value of R for LiCl in glass is remarkably small, the value increasing from 3.44 to 5.57 corresponding to concentrations 0.47 to 2.26/1000 g. The values of R for LiCl in the pure crystal and at infinite dilution in aqueous solution are respectively 7.59 and 8.76. The positive slope of the curve is quite pronounced. It may be mentioned in this connection that LiClO_4 also gives a positive slope in aqueous solution, although LiCl as usual gives a negative slope. For NaCl , the increase in value of R is from 5.43 to 7.44 corresponding to a concentration increase from 0.87 to 3.21 g. equiv. salt/1000 g. borax. The values of R for the pure salt in the crystal and at infinite dilution are respectively 8.52 and 9.27. For KCl , the value increases from 9.02 to 9.81 for a concentration change from 1.04 to 2.20 g. equiv. salt/1000g borax. Thus it is clear that *qualitatively* the effect of concentration on the mole-refraction of the dissolved salt follows the inequality $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$, as can be expected from Fajan's Deformation Theory.

The case of NaI dissolved in borax stands out in prominent contrast with its behaviour in aqueous solution. In aqueous solution NaI gives a very steep negative slope in the concentration—refraction curve. In borax solution on the contrary there is an equally prominent positive slope, the value of R increasing from 10.53 to 14.20 between a concentration increase 0.21 and 0.62 g. equiv. salt/1000 g. borax. The question of cationic exchange between the salt and the solvent to which reference has been made does not arise in this case as well as in the case of NaCl . It is clear therefore that while in aqueous solution, the refractometric evidence points to a large dissociation even in concentrated solution, in solution in borax glass, it shows considerably decreased dissociation and a very considerable deformation.